

"YASHIL IQTISODIYOT VA TARAQQIYOT"

IV GLOBAL VA MILLIY IQTISODIYOT TRENDLARI: "O'ZBEKISTON - 2030" STRATEGIYASI

23-24 OKTYABR

23-24 OCTOBER 2025

2030 UZBEKISTAN STRATEGY

CONFERENCE "GLOBAL AND NATIONAL ECONOMIC TRENDS"

TOSHKENT DAVLAT IQTISODIYOT UNIVERSITETI

FORUM "2030" GLOBAL VA UZBEKISTON - 2030 STRATEGIYA "GLOBAL AND NATIONAL ECONOMIC TRENDS: UZBEKISTON-2030" STRATEGIYA "ГЛОБАЛЬНЫЕ И НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЕ ТЕНДЕНЦИИ: СТРАТЕГИЯ «УЗБЕКИСТАН -2030»"

GLOBAL VA MILLIY IQTISODIYOT TRENDLARI: "O'ZBEKISTON - 2030" STRATEGIYASI
GLOBAL AND NATIONAL ECONOMIC TRENDS: "UZBEKISTON-2030" STRATEGY
ГЛОБАЛЬНЫЕ И НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЕ ТЕНДЕНЦИИ: СТРАТЕГИЯ «УЗБЕКИСТАН -2030»

YASHIL IQTISODIYOT VA TARAQQIYOT

2025

ELEKTRON ILMIY JURNAL

MAXSUS SON

- MACROECONOMIC STABILITY
•LABOR MARKET IN THE GREEN ECONOMY
•GLOBAL ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL ECONOMIC RELATIONS
•GREEN INVESTMENT AND FINANCING
•GREEN TECHNOLOGIES
•ECO-TOURISM
•GREEN INNOVATIONS

CONFERENCE "GLOBAL AND NATIONAL ECONOMIC TRENDS"

TASHKENT STATE UNIVERSITY OF ECONOMICS

2nd CONFERENCE ON BANKING / FINANCIAL DIRECTION OF THE PRIVATE SECTOR

2030

BANK-MOLIYA TIZIMI VA XUSUSIY SEKTORNI RIVOJLANTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI

**TOSHKENT DAVLAT
IQTISODIYOT UNIVERSITETI**

**IV GLOBAL VA MILLIY
IQTISODIYOT TRENDLARI:
“O‘ZBEKISTON – 2030”
STRATEGIYASI FORUMI**

(MAXSUS SON)

TOSHKENT–2025

Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:

Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

ISBN: 978-9910-8110-8-1

UO'K: 004.89(575.1)(062)

KBK: 32.813(5O')ya1

T 97

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayeich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Maxmudov Nosir, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xajiyev Baxtiyor Dushaboyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor
Ali Konak (Ali Ko'nak), iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor (Turkiya)
Cham Tat Huei, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD), professor (Malayziya)
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldixo'ja o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dots.
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, O'z.Respub. Bosh prokuraturasi boshqarma boshlig'i o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farkhod, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Bosh prokuraturasi IJQKD boshlig'i
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), katta o'qituvchi
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), v.b. dots.
Djudi Smetana, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Krissi Lyuis, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (Moskva)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD) (Turkiya)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon o'g'li, TDIU ITI departamenti rahbari
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent.

Editorial board:

Salimov Okil Umrzokovich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjayeich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Rae Kwon Chung, South Korea, Honorary Professor at TSUE, Nobel Prize Laureate
Osman Mesten, Member of the Turkish Parliament, Head of the Turkey–Uzbekistan Friendship Society
Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayeich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhriddinovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences
Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Makhmudov Nosir, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor
Slizovskiy Dmitriy Yegorovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abduganiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khakimov Nazar Khakimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Professor
Ali Konak, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor (Turkey)
Cham Tat Huei, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)
Foziljonov Ibrokhimjon Sotvoldikhoja ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Head of Department, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan
Ochilov Farkhod, Head of DCEC, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan
Buzrukkhonov Sarvarkhon Munavvarkhonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences
Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences, Senior Lecturer
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Acting Associate Professor
Judi Smetana, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Chrissy Lewis, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Glazova Marina Victorovna, Doctor of Sciences in Economics (Moscow))
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (Turkey)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon ugli, Head of the Department of Scientific Research and Innovations, TSUE
Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli, Senior lecturer at TSUI
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor.

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, katta o'qituvchi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, mustaqil tadqiqotchi
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Geografiya fanlari doktori, professori
Umirzoqov Ja'sur Artiqboy o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent
Zebo Kuldasheva, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Pulatov Bakhtiyor Alimovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Rustamov Ilkhomiddin, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Khakimov Ziyodulla Akhmadovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics
Gafurov Doniyor Orifovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy
Fayziyev Oybek Rakhimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Tukhtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Khamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarimovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Yakhshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, Senior Lecturer
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, Independent Researcher
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Doctor of Geographical Sciences, Professor
Umirzokov Jasur Artiqboy ugli, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor
Zebo Kuldasheva, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi
Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar
vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy
attestatsiya komissiyasi
rayosatining
2023-yil 1-apreldagi
336/3-sonli qarori bilan
ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

INNOVATSION SIYOSATNI AMALGA OSHIRISHNING USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI – OLIY TA'LIM TRANSFORMATSIYASI, RAQAMLI MODERNIZATSIYA VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH OMILLARI.....	13
Sharipov Kongratbay Avezimbetovich	
O'ZBEKISTON YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISHI: ZARURAT, MAQSADI VA AYRIM MUAMMOLARI, YECHIMLAR	16
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna	
FAN, TA'LIM VA ISHLAB CHIQRISHDAGI SO'NGGI TENDENSIYALAR VA INNOVATSIYALAR	25
To'ychiyev Olimjon Alijonovich	
QURILISH TASHKILOTLARIDA KREDITGA LAYOQATLILIKNI BAHOLASHNI RAQAMLASHTIRISH	30
Mavlanov Normo'min Normamatovich	
BUDJET TASHKILOTLARIDA DAVLAT XARIDLARINI SAMARALI TASHKIL ETISHDA ELEKTRON SAVDOLARNING AHAMIYATI.....	37
Turabov Sarvar Abdulmalikovich	
O'ZBEKISTONNI MINTAQAVIY TA'LIM VA ILM-FAN HABIGA AYLANTIRISHNING ISTIQBOLLI YO'NALISHLARI	41
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Maxamatjon o'g'li	
HUDUDIY RIVOJLANISH STRATEGIYALARIGA INNOVATSION KOMPONENTLARNI INTEGRATSIYA QILISH USULLARI	46
Muminov Fazliddin Xusniddin o'g'li	
OROL DENGIZI MEROSI: EKOLOGIK FOJIANI BARQAROR EKOTURIZM IMKONIYATLARIGA AYLANTIRISH	52
Zufarova Nozima	
KORXONALARNING YASHIL MARKETING STRATEGIYASINI ISHLAB CHIQISH METODOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	60
Ergashxodjayeva Shaxnoza Djasurovna	
O'ZBEKISTONDA ISHCHI KUCHI BOZORINING TAKRORIY AMAL QILISHINING NAZARIY JIHATLARI	66
Mamaraximov B.E.	
BANK-MOLIYA TIZIMIDA QIMMATLI QOG'OZLAR VA MOLIYAVIY INSTRUMENTLARDAN FOYDALANISH ORQALI GAROV DIVERSIFIKATSIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI.....	70
Xolbozorov Husniddin Norbek o'g'li	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA TO'QIMACHILIK SANOATIDA MARKETINGNING INNOVATSION KONSEPSIYALARI.....	76
Jumayev Olimjon Sadulloevich, Axmedova Shoxsanam Sindbod qizi	
SAVDO KORXONALARIDA EKOLOGIK MAHSULOTLARNI TARG'IB QILISH VA SOTISHNI RAG'BATLANTIRISH USULLARI	84
Jalalova Dildora Jamolovna	
DIRECTIONS OF FORMING AND PROVIDING A COMPETITIVE EXPORT-ORIENTED ECONOMY IN UZBEKISTAN	87
Asatullaev Khurshid Sunatullaevich, Nasirkhodjaeva Dilafruz Sabitkhanovna, Abdullayeva Madina Kamilovna	
FROM SCIENCE TO BUSINESS: HOW UNIVERSITIES STIMULATE INNOVATION	94
Prof. A. Bobozhonov, Prof. A.M. Shatre, Assoc. Prof. V. Kirilova Vladimirova, prof. R.Kh. Karlibaeva	
PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF GREEN TECHNOLOGIES IN UZBEKISTAN BASED ON ADVANCED INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE	100
Otamuratov Sarvar	
SPECIFIC FEATURES OF MIGRATION FROM UZBEKISTAN AND PROSPECTS FOR ORGANIZATIONAL IMPROVEMENT	105
Sabiroya Lola Shavkatovna, Shaislamova Nargiza Kabilovna	

KORXONA BARQAROR AXBOROT TIZIMINI YARATISH QIYINCHILIKLARI.....	112
Abidov Abdujabbar Abduxamidovich	
TIJORAT BANKLARI FAOLIYATIGA FOIZ RISKINING TA'SIRI VA ILMIY-NAZARIY ASOSLARI.....	119
Isakov.J.Ya	
CREATION OF A MECHANISM FOR THE DEVELOPMENT AND INTRODUCTION OF A MODEL OF COMPLETE TRANSITION TO THE NETZERO ENERGY SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN	127
Makhmudova Guljakhon N., Gulomova Nigora Farxadovna	
УСИЛЕНИЕ ВОЗДЕЙСТВИЯ ХОЗЯЙСТВЕННОГО МЕХАНИЗМА НА СТОИМОСТНУЮ ОЦЕНКУ ОСНОВНЫХ ФАКТОРОВ ПРОИЗВОДСТВА.....	133
Алишер Расулев, Сергей Воронин	
РОЛЬ ФИНАНСОВОЙ ГЛОБАЛИЗАЦИИ В РАЗВИТИИ МАЛОГО И СРЕДНЕГО ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСТВА: ПЕРСПЕКТИВА И ПРИКЛАДНЫЕ РЕШЕНИЯ ДЛЯ ИХ ПЕРЕХОДА К МСФО.....	143
Эргашева Шахло Тургуновна	
DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS OF AGRICULTURAL ECONOMIC ACTIVITY UNDER DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION	151
Boburjon Vafoev	
ENERGETIKA TIZIMIDAGI KORXONALAR MOLIYAVIY HOLATINING TAHLILI.....	157
Matnazar Yusupovich Raximov	
АСПЕКТЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ РАЗВИТИЕМ ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО ТУРИЗМА В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ.....	162
Очилова Хилола Фармоновна	
TA'LIM XIZMATLARI BOZORINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLAR.....	167
Abdullayev Suyun Artikovich	
THE INTERCONNECTION BETWEEN DIGITAL LEARNING PLATFORMS AND THE DIGITAL ECONOMY.....	171
Kuchkarov Takhir Safarovich, Kholmonov Shodiyor Karshiboyevich	
BANK-MOLIYA TIZIMI VA XUSUSIY SEKTORNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA YANGI TEXNOLOGIYALAR YORDAMIDA BANK FAOLIYATINI RAQAMLASHTIRISH IMKONIYATLARI	174
Norov Akmal Ruzimamatovich	
РАЗВИТИЕ БАНКОВСКО-ФИНАНСОВОЙ СИСТЕМЫ И ЧАСТНОГО СЕКТОРА В РАМКАХ ПЕРСПЕКТИВ ВСТУПЛЕНИЯ ВО ВСЕМИРНУЮ ТОРГОВУЮ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЮ	180
У.А.Юлдашева	
ЗЕЛЕННЫЕ ПОТРЕБИТЕЛИ - ПУТИ РАЗВИТИЯ ЗЕЛЕННОГО РОСТА В РАМКАХ УСТОЙЧИВОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ	185
Дехканова Наргиза Шарифовна	
ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИЙ АУДИТ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	192
Ходжаева М.Х.	
TADBIRKORLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA AHOLINING MOLIYAVIY SAVODXONLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI.....	199
Akbarova Barno Shuxratovna	
SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC GROWTH THROUGH TOURISM UNDER THE GREEN ECONOMY FRAMEWORK	204
Jumayev Akbar Mahmudovich	
МАКРОИQTISODIY BARQARORLIKNI TA'MINLASHDA BANK TIZIMINI RIVOJLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	210
Erkinxojiyev Ismoiljon Ikromjon o'g'li	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA MINTAQAVIY SANOAT KORXONALARIDA KORPORATIV MADANIYATNI RIVOJLANTIRISH VA BOSHQARUV SAMARADORLIGINI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH.....	216
Matrizayeva Dilaram Yusupbayevna	
UZBEKISTAN AT THE CROSSROADS OF HISTORY AND GREEN INNOVATION: FROM THE GREAT SILK ROAD TO A SUSTAINABLE FUTURE	220
Avalova Gulshod Murodullayevna	

ГЛАВНЫЕ ВЕКТОРЫ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОЙ ПОЛИТИКИ ПО ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЮ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	226
Абдуллаева М.К.	
ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT IN THE INDUSTRIAL CLUSTERS SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN: MODERN TRENDS AND DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS.....	233
Kholikova Rukhsora Sanjarovna	
HUDUDDAGI KICHIK BIZNESNING SAMARALI TARKIBIY TUZILMASINI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA MUTASSADI TASHKILOTLARNING O‘ZARO UYG‘UN HARAKATINI TASHKIL ETISH.....	239
Sharipov Kuvondik Baxtiyorovich	
BUSINESS ANALYTICS IN HISTORICAL PERSPECTIVE: LESSONS FROM THE INDUSTRIAL REVOLUTION TO THE DIGITAL AGE	246
Burxonova Sabo Tulanovna	
“COST ENGINEERING”NING NAZARIY ASOSLARI VA UNI IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIKNI OSHIRISHDAGI O‘RNI.....	252
Zaynitdinova Umida Djalalovna	
FEATURES AND WAYS OF FURTHER DEVELOPMENT OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY.....	256
Kobilov Alisher, Majidova Irodahon	
ПИЩЕВАЯ ИНДУСТРИЯ УЗБЕКИСТАНА: АГРАРНЫЙ ИМПУЛЬС, ЭНЕРГЕТИЧЕСКОЕ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЕ И ЦЕНОВАЯ КОНЪЮНКТУРА.....	263
Юлдашев Голибжон Тургунович, Элдорбеков Гофурбек Искандарбек угли	
INCOME INEQUALITY AND MACROECONOMIC DETERMINANTS IN UZBEKISTAN: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS	273
Muhammad Eid Balbaa, Marina Sagatovna Abdurashidova	
РЫНОК ТРУДА В УСЛОВИЯХ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ЗЕЛЕННОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	276
Амирджанова Ситора Суннат кизи	
EKOLOGIK QO‘RIQXONALARDA MONITORING JARAYONLARINING IQTISODIY VA TASHKILIY ANAMIYATI.....	282
Homidov Hamdam Hasan o‘g‘li	
ГАРМОНИЗАЦИЯ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ СТАНДАРТОВ БУХГАЛТЕРСКОГО УЧЕТА В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН В СООТВЕТСТВИИ С МСФО	288
Абдужалилова Дилноз Абдусаттаровна	
SUSTAINABLE TOURISM AND BIODIVERSITY PROTECTION: CASE OF UZBEKISTAN WITHIN THE UNESCO WORLD HERITAGE FRAMEWORK.....	294
Yuldasheva Dilnoza Ulugbekovna	
ПРАКТИЧЕСКОЕ ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ НЕЙРОМАРКЕТИНГА НА МАРКЕТПЛЕЙСАХ (WILDBERRIES, UZUM MARKET, ЯНДЕКС МАРКЕТ)	300
Юлдашев Жамшид Абрарович	
ЗЕЛЕНАЯ ЭКОНОМИКА КАК СТИМУЛ РАЗВИТИЯ РЫНКА ТРУДА УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	309
Шаюсупова Наргиза Тургуновна	
GLOBALLASHUV SHAROITIDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANISHI O‘ZBEKISTONNING XALQARO SAVDOSIGA VA IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGIGA TAHDID SIFATIDA.....	315
Mamatov Mamajan Ahmadjonovich	
SUG‘URTA TASHKILOTLARI FAOLIYATI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH VA INNOVATSION SUG‘URTA MAHSULOTLARINI JORIY QILISH MASALALARI	321
Xalikulova Gulzada Tadjimuratovna	
O‘ZBEKISTON OZIQ-OVQAT BOZORIDA YASHIL MARKETING STRATEGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH ORQALI BARQAROR ISTE‘MOLNI RAG‘BATLANTIRISH	333
Eshmatov Sanjar Azimqulovich	
ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ЗЕЛЁНЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ В РАЗНЫХ ОТРАСЛЯХ ЭКОНОМИКИ: ГЛОБАЛЬНЫЙ ОПЫТ И НАЦИОНАЛЬНАЯ ПРАКТИКА	337
Назарова Ра‘но Рустамовна, Мусаева Гавхар Ахматжон кизи	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTDA MEHNAT BOZORI: O‘ZBEKISTON TAJRIBASI VA ISTIQBOLLARI.....	343
Homidjonov Fozilxon Umarxon o‘g‘li, Haydarov Kamoliddin Baratovich	

GREEN INVESTMENT: PATHWAYS TOWARD A SUSTAINABLE FUTURE.....	348
Odilova Sitora Sayfitdin kizi	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA O'ZBEKISTON SANOAT KORXONALARIDA MARKETING STRATEGIYALARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	351
Kutbitdinova Mohigul Inoyatovna	
QURILISH MATERIALLARI SANOATIDA YASHIL TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYANING BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHGA TA'SIRI	356
Metyakubov Azamat Djumanazarovich	
ELEKTR SANOAT KORXONALARINING IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA MARKETING VOSITALARIDAN FOYDALANISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	361
Tursunxo'jayev Sardor Jamoliddin o'g'li	
УЧЕТ ЗАТРАТ И МЕТОДЫ ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЯ СЕБЕСТОИМОСТИ ПРОДУКЦИИ В НЕФТЕГАЗОВОЙ ОТРАСЛИ	368
Махкамова Саида Гайратовна	
MILLIY HISOBLAR TIZIMIDA INTELLEKTUAL MULK MAHSULOTLARINI MAKROIQTISODIY DARAJADA HISOBGA OLISHNING METODOLOGIK ASOSI.....	375
Sunnatov Muxtor Ne'matovich	
RENEWABLE ENERGY AND MACROECONOMIC STABILITY IN CENTRAL ASIA: PATHWAYS WITHIN THE GREEN ECONOMY	382
Khabibullo Abdullaev	
JAHON SUG'URTA AMALIYOTI ASOSIDA O'ZBEKISTON SUG'URTA BOZORIDA YANGI RIVOJLANISH YO'NALISHLARI.....	387
Abdimovminova Saodat Taxirjonovna	
INTEGRATING DATA SCIENCE INTO GREEN FINANCING AND ECO-INNOVATIONS: ACHIEVING THE GOALS OF UZBEKISTAN-2030	397
Norboev Odil Abraevich, Kungratov Ilmurod Kuzibay ugli	
O'ZBEKISTONDA SANOAT ISHLAB CHIQRISHINI DIVERSIFIKATSIYALASH AMALIYOTI VA ISTIQBOLLARI	404
Olimov Maqsudjon Komiljon o'g'li	
СОЗДАНИЕ ЗЕЛЕННОГО ЭНЕРГЕТИЧЕСКОГО КОРИДОРА В ЕВРОПУ: РЕГИОНАЛЬНЫЙ ПОТЕНЦИАЛ АЗЕРБАЙДЖАНА, КАЗАХСТАНА И УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	411
Лала Гамидова Адиль, Арзуман Гусейнов Айдын	
MAHALLA TIZIMIDA AHOLINI OZIQ-OVQAT MAHSULOTLARIGA BO'LGAN ISTE'MOL TALABLARI MODEL.....	419
S. Qulmatova	
AHOLI ICHKI MIGRATSIYASINING MEHNAT BOZORIGA TA'SIRINI STATISTIK O'RGANISH	427
Mirolimov Mirislom Mirshokir o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTONDA BANK TIZIMINI RAQAMLASHTIRISH TENDENSIYALARI VA MUAMMOLARI	434
Jumaniyozova Mukaddas Yuldashevna	
ЗЕЛЁНЫЕ ФИНАНСЫ: ГЛОБАЛЬНЫЕ ТРЕНДЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	438
Фаттахова Муниса	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI SOHASI FAOLIYATINI DAVLAT TOMONIDAN MUVOFIQLASHTIRISH VA BOSHQARISH MEKANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	444
Tuxtamishev Shodimurod Qurbonboyevich	
MARKETING TADQIQOTLARI ASOSIDA MEVA-SABZAVOT MAHSULOTLARI EKSPORT SALONIYATINI OSHIRISH	452
Xojiyev Elshod Yoqub o'g'li	
СПОСОБЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ НАУЧНЫМИ УЧРЕЖДЕНИЯМИ В ЦЕЛЯХ ПЕРЕХОДА НА РАЗРАБОТКУ ЗЕЛЕННЫХ ИННОВАЦИЙ	459
Юдаков Александр Андреевич	
O'ZBEKISTONNI JAHON SAVDO TASHKILOTIGA A'ZO BO'LISHINING OZIQ-OVQAT XAVFSIZLIGINI TA'MINLASHGA TA'SIRI.....	466
Axmedova N.A.	

O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA KLASTERLAR FAOLIYATINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING IQTISODIY MEKANIZMI	471
Sherkulov Shohruh Erkin o'g'li	
DEVELOPMENT SCENARIOS OF UZBEKISTAN'S ACTIVE LABOR FORCE UNTIL 2030 AND THEIR ECONOMIC IMPLICATIONS.....	476
Ganiev Bakhtiyor Zulfikor ugli, Rakhmonov Bekzod Sharibjon ugli	
РАЗВИТИЕ ЗЕЛЁНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ КАК ФАКТОР СТИМУЛИРОВАНИЯ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ АКТИВНОСТИ ЖЕНЩИН В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	481
Дониерова Фотимабону Алишер кизи	
YASHIL ENERGETIKA VA UNING IQTISODIY TARAQQIYOTDAGI O'RNI	488
Babadjanova Malika Ruzimova	
BENCHMARKING IN THE AUTOMOTIVE INDUSTRY: STRATEGIES FOR SUSTAINABLE COMPETITIVENESS	492
Abdurashidova Nigora	
УЗБЕКИСТАН СТРЕМИТСЯ К УСТОЙЧИВОМУ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОМУ РОСТУ, ВНЕДРЯЯ ПРИНЦИПЫ «ЗЕЛЁНОЙ» ЭКОНОМИКИ	498
Сагдуллаева Гулнора Ботыровна	
O'ZBEKISTONDA FAOLIYAT YURITAYOTGAN KOMPANIYALARNING GLOBAL MARKETING STRATEGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH YO'NALISHLARI.....	502
Sharipov Ixtiyor Baxtiyorovich	
ZAIF BANDLIKDAN UNUMLI BANDLIK SARI TRANSFORMATSIYA: O'ZINI O'ZI BAND QILISH	507
Qurbonov Samandar Pulatovich	
ВОЗОБНОВЛЯЕМАЯ ЭНЕРГИЯ В ГЛОБАЛЬНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКЕ: ТЕКУЩИЕ ТЕНДЕНЦИИ И БУДУЩЕЕ РАЗВИТИЕ.....	514
Меҳрибан Самедова Тофик	
RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNING MEHNAT UNUMDORLIGINI OSHIRISHGA TA'SIRI	521
Zafar Alisherovich Mamadiev, Nodira Isametdinovna Xasanxonova	
SAVDO KORXONALARIDA BUXGALTERIYA HISOBINI XALQARO STANDARTLARGA INTEGRATSIYA QILISH MEKANIZMLARI.....	526
Ablazov Lazizbek Abdiquosimovich	
TIJORAT BANKLARINING TRANSFORMATSIYASI JARAYONINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	530
Ziyadullaev Z.	
TO'LOV TIZIMI KONSEPTUAL MODELINING SHAKLLANISH TAMOYILLARI	537
Toshniyozov Sherali Kamoliddinovich	
STAFF PERFORMANCE EVALUATION BASED ON KPI SYSTEM INDICATORS.....	546
Rakhmatullaeva Shakhnoza Khamidovna, Sadriddinova Sevinchkhon	
SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT AND THE TRANSITION TO A GREEN ECONOMY IN THE CONTEXT OF GLOBAL ECONOMIC TRENDS	555
Svetlana Yurievna Shatokhina	
MILLIY TARBIYA OMILLARI VA MILLIY MADANIY YONDASHUV ASOSIDA TALABALARDA O'QUV TASHABBUSKORLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING NAZARIY-AMALIY ASOSLARI.....	560
Azimova Nilufar Nuriddinovna	
TIJORAT BANKLARI TOMONIDAN KICHIK BIZNES SUBYEKTLARINI TA'MINLASHDA BANK RESURSLARINING ROLI	567
Xodjayeva Jeyrona Ravshonbek qizi	
O'QUV DASTURINI INTEGRATSIYALASH VA YASHIL KO'NIKMALARNI RIVOJLANTIRISH: AKADEMIK VA SANOAT O'RTASIDAGI TAFOVUTNI YOPISH	572
Qo'ziqulova Dilfuzaxon Maxammatisaqovna	
DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION AND DIGITAL PLATFORMS AS A KEY FACTOR IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESS ENTITIES	580
Rizayeva Nilufar Oblakulovna	

IQTISODIY OLIY TA'LIMDA STRATEGIK INNOVATSIYALAR: YASHIL KO'NIKMALARNI MILLIY VA GLOBAL BARQARORLIK MAQSADLARI BILAN MUVOFIQLASHTIRISH	585
<i>Xasanova Zarina Maxamadaliyeva</i>	
MARKAZIY OSIYODA YASHIL IQTISODIYOT: BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH YO'LIDAGI TO'SIQLAR VA ISTIQBOLLAR.....	594
<i>Aminov Shovkat O'ktam o'g'li</i>	
ПЕСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ЗЕЛЁНЫХ ОБЛИГАЦИЙ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	598
<i>Саидахмедова Аида Мирзаевна</i>	
ПОВЫШЕНИЕ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ И СНИЖЕНИЕ РИСКОВ КОММЕРЧЕСКИХ БАНКОВ НА ОСНОВЕ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ ТРАНЗАКЦИЙ В ФИНАНСОВЫХ ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫХ СИСТЕМАХ С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ СИММЕТРИЧНЫХ КРИПТОСИСТЕМ.....	605
<i>Раҳимбердиев Қ.Б.</i>	
ИНТЕГРАЦИЯ ФИНАНСОВЫХ И СТРАХОВЫХ ИНСТРУМЕНТОВ ДЛЯ СТИМУЛИРОВАНИЯ УСТОЙЧИВОГО ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РОСТА	612
<i>Ш.Ф.Кобилжонова</i>	
СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ КАПИТАЛА ХОЗЯЙСТВУЮЩИХ СУБЪЕКТОВ В КОНТЕКСТЕ РАЗВИТИЯ БАНКОВСКО-ФИНАНСОВОЙ СИСТЕМЫ И ЧАСТНОГО СЕКТОРА ЭКОНОМИКИ	618
<i>Д.А.Юлдашева</i>	
РОЛЬ БАНКОВСКО-ФИНАНСОВОЙ СИСТЕМЫ И СТРАХОВЫХ МЕХАНИЗМОВ В СТИМУЛИРОВАНИИ РАЗВИТИЯ ЧАСТНОГО СЕКТОРА	624
<i>Г.Т.Ахмедова</i>	
SUG'URTA BOZORI FAOLIYATINI RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA TRANSFORMATSIYALASH VA UNING RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISH MASALALARI.....	630
<i>Saidov Farrux Faxriddinovich</i>	
OPPORTUNITIES TO ENSURE SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC GROWTH IN THE ENERGY SECTOR THROUGH THE TRANSITION TO A GREEN ECONOMY.....	635
<i>Ulashov Aliboy Rashid ugli, Istamova Nasiba Narzillo kizi</i>	
INKLYUZIV OLIY TA'LIMDA MUSTAQIL ISHLASH JARAYONINI TASHKILLASHTIRISH.....	641
<i>Akbarova Kamola Abdujabbor qizi</i>	
YOUTH-DRIVEN PATHWAYS TO GREEN EMPLOYMENT: A THEORETICAL EXAMINATION OF INCLUSIVE ECONOMIC STRATEGIES	646
<i>Suvpulatov Ozodjon Alijon ugli</i>	
KICHIK BIZNES INFRATUZILMASINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA XORIJIY TAJRIBALAR VA UNING O'ZBEKISTON UCHUN AHAMIYATI	651
<i>Botirova Xulkar Olimjonovna</i>	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH KLASTERLARI: NAZARIY ASOSLAR VA AMALIY YONDASHUVLAR.....	655
<i>Sherkulova Nodirabegim Baxordin qizi</i>	
BIOTECHNOLOGICAL SOLUTIONS IN URBAN PLANNING: OPPORTUNITIES AND LIMITATIONS OF "LIQUID TREES"	660
<i>Nosirkulov Asadjon Ahmadjon ugli</i>	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA TIKLANADIGAN ENERGIYA MANBALARINING O'RNI.....	663
<i>Fayziyeva Dilso'z Bahodirovna</i>	
KREDIT PORTFELIDA MUAMMOLI KREDITLAR ULUSHINI KAMAYTIRISH YO'LLARI	668
<i>Salixova G.J</i>	
O'ZBEKISTONDA KANDOLAT MAHSULOTLARI BOZORINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA YASHIL MARKETING STRATEGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH.....	672
<i>Boboyorova Maftuna Xaqqul qizi, Boboyorov Islombek Xaqqul o'g'li</i>	
OLIJ TA'LIM TIZIMIDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNI QO'LLASH METODLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	675
<i>Xusniddinov Yorqinjon Muhiddin o'g'li</i>	

MODA SANOATIDA CRM TIZIMLARINI ELEKTRON SAVDO PLATFORMALARI BILAN UYG'UNLASHTIRISHDAGI TO'SIQLAR	679
Xalilova Nafisa Komilovna	
ENHANCING FOREIGN ECONOMIC RELATIONS AS A DRIVING FACTOR IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE NATIONAL ECONOMY	683
Khaitova Feruza Bahrom kizi	
MARKAZIY OSIYO MAMLAKATLARIDA XORIJIY INVESTITSIYALARNING QAYTA TIKLANUVCHI ENERGIYA MANBALARIGA TA'SIRI	687
Akishova Shaxnoza Davlet qizi	
BUXORO VILOYATIDA HUNARMANDCHILIK FAOLIYATINING RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYALARI: TAHLIL VA ISTIQBOLLAR.....	693
Ravshanova Gulchexra Ravshanovna	
SANOATNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING MEKANIZMLARI TURLARI VA OLIMLARNING YONDASHUVLARI	698
Ne'matov Shoxruxbek Ma'murjon o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTON BANK-MOLIYA TIZIMIDA KREDIT RISKLARINI BOSHQARISH AMALIYOTINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH VA UNING XUSUSIY SEKTOR RIVOJLANISHIGA TA'SIRI.....	703
Norova Nozima Nabiyevna	
O'ZBEKISTON BANK-MOLIYA TIZIMIDA REAL SEKTORNI KREDITLASH MEKANIZMLARINI SAMARALI JORIY ETISH VA XUSUSIY SEKTOR RIVOJIGA TA'SIRI.....	709
Abduxomidov Ikromjon Maxamadin o'g'li	
MOLIYA TIZIMIDA BOJ-TARIF SIYOSATINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH VA XUSUSIY SEKTOR RIVOJLANISHIGA TA'SIRI (OZIQ-OVQAT IMPORTI MISOLIDA).....	715
Rizaev Mirmahmud Xotamjanovich	
YASHIL MARKETING VA ESG INTEGRATSIYASI: STATISTIK TAHLIL VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI	721
Charos G'ayratova	
ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ НАПРАВЛЕНИЯ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОГО КАПИТАЛА ДЛЯ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ УСТОЙЧИВОГО ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РОСТА В УСЛОВИЯХ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ «ЗЕЛЁНОЙ» ЭКОНОМИКИ.....	727
Г.А.Хайитбаева	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISH SHAROITIDA TIJORAT BANKLAR TOMONIDAN TADBIRKORLIK FAOLIYATINI KREDITLASH.....	734
Tajiddinov Jamshiddin Shamsutdinovich	
IQTISODIYOTNING TARKIBIY TRANSFORMATSIYASIGA XORIJIY INVESTITSIYALAR TA'SIRINI BAHOLASH MEKANIZMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	738
Shodiboyeva Dilzoda Farhodjon qizi	
MOLIYA TIZIMI BARQARORLIGI VA BUDJET TUSHUMLARINI OSHIRISHDA TASHQI IQTISODIY FAOLIYATNING AHAMIYATI.....	743
Aktamov Akbarjon Aslan o'g'li	
ENSURING SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC GROWTH IN THE TRANSITION TO A GREEN ECONOMY: AN ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CARBON EMISSIONS AND ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT.....	748
Shakhriddinova Sitara Tolibjon kizi	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISH JARAYONIDA TIJORAT BANKLARIDA INVESTITSIYA LOYIHALARI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA ESG TAMOYILLARINING ROLI	760
Ostonaqulova Gulchehraxon Muhammadyoqub qizi	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT TAMOYILLARI ASOSIDA SANOAT KORXONALARIDA YETKAZIB BERISH STRATEGIYALARINI ISHLAB CHIQISH	769
Yusupov Ulug'bek Mamayusupovich	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT KONTEKSTIDA MAKROIQTISODIY BARQARORLIKNI MUSTAHKAMLASH: XALQARO TAJRIBA VA O'ZBEKISTON AMALIYOTI.....	776
Isroilov Islomiddin Kamoliddin o'g'li	

RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA SHAROITIDA SPORT TASHKILOTLARINING YANGI BIZNES MODELLARINI ISHLAB CHIQISH	782
G'ulomov Musirmon	
O'ZBEKISTONDA IQTISODIYOTGA XORIJIY INVESTISIYALARNI JALB ETISHNING USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI VA ISTIQBOLLARI	786
Sharipova Shahnoza Baxtiyorovna	
O'ZBEKISTONDA INVESTISIYA MUHITIGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR VA INVESTISIYALARNING IQTISODIYOTGA JALB ETILISH HOLATI TAHLILI	795
Karimova Qunduz Atanazarovna	
O'ZBEKISTON TURISTIK XIZMATLAR BOZORIDA BANDLIK TRANSFORMATSIYASINI VA UNI TARTIBGA SOLISH HOLATINI TAHLIL QILISH	804
To'xtayeva Xurshida Farxodovna	
INVESTITSIYA LOYIHALARIGA TA'SIR QILUVCHI INVESTITSIYA RISKLARINI BAHOLASH.....	811
Zohidova Ruksora Komiljon qizi	
ТИПЫ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ ФИНАНСОВЫХ РАЗВЕДОК: ОСНОВНЫЕ РАЗЛИЧИЯ, ФОРМЫ И МЕТОДЫ ОСУЩЕСТВЛЕНИЯ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ.....	817
Эсанов Шохрух Отабекович	
FACE RECOGNITION PROGRAM IN PYTHON.....	823
Khurramova Maftunakhon Zhurabekovna, Khurramov Azizjon Bakhodir ugli	
FORMATION OF ACCOUNTING POLICY FOR INTANGIBLE ASSETS.....	827
Farxod T. Abdvaxidov, Ramazon A. Abdurakhmanov	
O'ZBEKISTON EKSPORT TARKIBINI YUQORI QO'SHIMCHA QIYMATLI MAHSULOTLARGA O'TKAZISH STRATEGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	834
Raximov Eshmurod Normuradovich	
EKSPORT FAOLIYATIDA ERKIN IQTISODIY ZONALARNING SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI.....	838
Berdivaliyeva Madina Komiljon qizi	
TURIZM KLASTERLARIDA TIBBIY XIZMATLAR INTEGRATSIYASI: XALQARO TAJRIBA VA O'ZBEKISTON AMALIYOTI	841
Yazdanova Shohista Tuyg'un qizi Farxodova Shohnoza Umidbek qizi	
O'ZBEKISTON HAVO TRANSPORTI TIZIMINING JAHON IQTISODIYOTIDAGI O'RNI VA RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	850
Azimova Moxinur Nozimovna	

ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT IN THE INDUSTRIAL CLUSTERS SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN: MODERN TRENDS AND DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS

Kholikova Rukhsora Sanjarovna

Ph.D., Associate Professor, Department "Green Economy",
Tashkent State University of Economics

Email: r.xoliqova@tsue.uz

ORCID: 0000-0001-7672-6869

Abstract: The article discusses the features of the implementation of environmental management in industrial clusters of Uzbekistan. The current state of environmental policy in industrial zones is analyzed, problems are identified, and ways to improve environmental control and sustainable development are proposed.

Key words: Environmental management; industrial cluster; green economy; green energy; management; CO₂; pollution.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada O'zbekistonning sanoat klasterlarida ekologik boshqaruvni joriy etishning o'ziga xos jihatlari muhokama qilinadi. Sanoat zonalarida ekologik siyosatning hozirgi holati tahlil qilinib, mavjud muammolar aniqlanadi hamda ekologik nazoratni takomillashtirish va barqaror rivojlanishni ta'minlash yo'llari taklif etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: ekologik boshqaruv; sanoat klasteri; yashil iqtisodiyot; yashil energetika; boshqaruv; CO₂; ifloslanish.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются особенности внедрения экологического менеджмента в промышленных кластерах Узбекистана. Анализируется текущее состояние экологической политики в промышленных зонах, выявляются проблемы и предлагаются пути совершенствования экологического контроля и обеспечения устойчивого развития.

Ключевые слова: экологический менеджмент; промышленный кластер; зелёная экономика; зелёная энергетика; менеджмент; CO₂; загрязнение.

INTRODUCTION

Environmental management is a set of management decisions and actions aimed at minimizing the negative impact of industrial activities on the environment. Environmental management is the management of the environment in order to reduce the harm that humans cause to nature. Its main goal is to preserve resources (water, air, forests) for future generations, without worsening our lives now. Simply put, this is a way to develop so that nature does not suffer.

In the context of the active development of industrial clusters in Uzbekistan, the formation of a sustainable environmental policy that takes into account the interests of both the economy and nature is of particular importance.

Environmental management includes planning, implementation, control and adjustment of environmental activities. Key components include environmental auditing, environmental impact assessment and environmental monitoring systems [1].

LITERATURE REVIEW

The theoretical foundations of the study of environmental management in industrial clusters are formed at the intersection of cluster theory, industrial ecology and the concept of sustainable development. The classical theory of clusters by M. Porter [2] ("The Competitive Advantage of Nations", 1990) laid the foundation for understanding that the territorial concentration of enterprises and related organizations allows achieving a synergistic effect, including in the field of environmental management. Work in the field of industrial ecology, starting with the study by F. Frosch and N. Gallopoulos [3] ("Strategies for Manufacturing", Scientific American, 1989), showed the possibilities of inter-firm exchange of resources and energy to form closed production cycles, which is especially relevant in cluster systems.

An important area is related to the institutionalization of environmental management through standards. Thus, D. Andrews [4] (Green Management: Principles and Examples, 1998) and later studies by A. Del Boria [5] (Environmental Management Systems and Clusters, Journal of Cleaner Production, 2006) showed that the use of ISO 14001 and EMAS at the level of individual enterprises becomes more effective when they are implemented on a cluster scale. This is confirmed by the works of N. Gibbs and J. Dixon [6] (Ecodesign and Cluster Development, Business Strategy and the Environment, 2002), which emphasize the role of joint technology procurement and collective monitoring.

Studies of eco-industrial parks have made a significant contribution. A classic example is the Kalundborg Industrial Symbiosis (Denmark), described by T. Chertov [7] (Industrial Symbiosis in Kalundborg, Journal of Industrial Ecology, 1994), where it was proven that the coordinating role of the management company is a key factor in sustainability. Similar conclusions were made by Asian researchers J. Lee and K. Park [8] (From Industrial Park to Eco-Industrial Park: Patterns of Development in Korea, Journal of Environmental Planning and Management, 2008), who showed the importance of multi-level regulation and government involvement.

Modern management research emphasizes the transition from a compliance approach to proactive strategies. Thus, the works of H. Merrill [9] (Collaborative Environmental Governance, 2010) and R. Hoffman [10] (Managing Sustainable Innovation in Clusters, Organization & Environment, 2014) focus on the need for cooperation between business, government and universities. In this context, multi-level management is distinguished: strategic level (cluster decarbonization strategies), tactical (energy efficiency programs) and operational (project offices for closing cycles).

A separate layer of research is related to green supply chains and product life cycles. The classic work by S. Srivastava [11] ("Green Supply-Chain Management: A State-of-the-Art Literature Review", International Journal of Management Reviews, 2007) demonstrated the importance of collective cooperation for reducing the carbon footprint in supply chains. LCA approaches are actively developing in clusters, which is confirmed by the research of M. Bauman [12] ("Life Cycle Assessment in Industrial Clusters", 2013), which considers methods for assessing the overall environmental profile.

Digitalization is also actively included in environmental management. According to S. Chen and H. Huang [13] ("Digitalization and Eco-Industrial Development", Sustainability, 2019), the use of IoT and digital platforms allows the formation of "virtual ecosystems" for the exchange of by-products. Research by J. Block [14] and colleagues ("Blockchain for Green Supply Chains", Journal of Cleaner Production, 2020) emphasizes that blockchain technologies ensure transparency and reliability of environmental reporting within clusters.

In the political and economic aspect, comparative studies are important. Thus, the works of P. Lombardi [15] ("Eco-Industrial Parks in the European Union", 2016) and Z. Zhang [16] ("Eco-Industrial Development in China", Journal of Cleaner Production, 2017) demonstrate that government support and tax incentives are key factors in the success of environmental management. In OECD countries, as noted by R. Andrews [17] ("Environmental Governance in Clusters", 2018), a combination of soft and hard regulatory instruments ensures sustainable results.

Finally, the literature increasingly raises the issue of developing integrated indices for assessing the environmental sustainability of clusters. The works of V. Mol [18] ("Measuring Eco-Efficiency in Clusters", Ecological Indicators, 2020) propose using a multi-index approach, including indicators of resource and energy intensity, emissions and the share of secondary raw materials. At the same time, researchers note a number of barriers: information asymmetry, a lack of LCA competencies, as well as difficulties in distributing benefits between participants [19] (Klewitz & Hansen, "Sustainability-Oriented Innovation in Clusters", 2014).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodological basis of the research is based on a comprehensive and interdisciplinary approach, including theoretical, empirical and applied methods of analysis. This is due to the multidimensionality of the category "environmental management" and the need to study its manifestations at the level of industrial clusters.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Features of industrial clusters in Uzbekistan.

An industrial cluster is an association of companies, factories, suppliers, and educational or scientific institutions that operate in the same field and are located close to each other. Industrial clusters in Uzbekistan are concentrated in regions such as Tashkent, Navoi, Andijan, and Bukhara. The main industries are chemical, textile, food, and construction. Below are the main areas and examples (Figure 1):

Figure 1. Main directions of cluster policy in Uzbekistan [6].

In the context of Uzbekistan, such clusters are actively developing in the textile, chemical, construction and agro-industrial industries. The application of environmental management in these clusters has a number of specific features:

1. Integration of enterprise efforts. Environmental management in a cluster requires coordination of actions between all participants. Joint environmental programs, common treatment facilities and collective environmental initiatives can significantly increase the effectiveness of environmental measures.
2. Economy of scale. Due to the concentration of production, it is possible to create a single environmental monitoring system, which reduces costs and improves the quality of environmental control.
3. Diversity of pollution sources. Enterprises with different types of emissions and waste can coexist in one cluster. This complicates the management system, requires an integrated approach to assessing the impact on the environment and developing measures to prevent pollution.
4. The need for centralized management. Effective environmental management in clusters involves the creation of a governing body or environmental coordination council responsible for compliance with standards, coordination between enterprises and the implementation of a sustainable development strategy.
5. Impact on populated areas. Many clusters are located near residential areas, which requires enhanced control over emissions, noise levels and production safety. Of particular importance is interaction with local authorities and public organizations.
6. The role of the state. In Uzbekistan, state support for clusters is accompanied by opportunities for the implementation of environmental initiatives - subsidies for green technologies, benefits for environmental certification and state programs for the modernization of production.

Table 1. Main pollutants by region (thousand tons) [5]

Region	CO ₂	SO ₂	NO _x
Tashkent	450	120	90
Navoi	670	200	130
Andijan	310	80	70
Bukhara	500	150	110

An analysis of the presented table of pollutant emissions by regions of Uzbekistan reveals differences in the level of air pollution. Let's take a closer look.

Analysis for each substance:

1. CO₂ (carbon dioxide):

- Highest emissions: Navoi - 670 thousand tons.

- Lowest emissions: Andijan - 310 thousand tons.

- Reasons: High CO₂ emissions in Navoi can be associated with intensive industrial activity (e.g. chemical and mining).

2. SO₂ (sulfur dioxide):

- Highest emissions: Navoi - 200 thousand tons.

- Lowest emissions: Andijan - 80 thousand tons.

- SO₂ is usually associated with the combustion of sulfur-containing fuels such as coal and fuel oil. Again, the industrial nature of Navoi causes high levels of pollution.

3. NO_x (nitrogen oxides):

- Largest emissions: Navoi - 130 thousand tons.

- Smallest emissions: Andijan - 70 thousand tons.

- NO_x are emitted into the atmosphere during high-temperature processes, such as the operation of thermal power plants and transport.

Figure 2. Distribution of CO₂ emissions by region [5]

As the graph on Distribution of CO₂ emissions by region shows, Navoi is the leader in overall pollution. The most environmentally “clean” of these is Andijan, although the level of emissions still remains significant. Navoi is the most polluted region among those presented by all the main indicators. This confirms the need for increased control over industrial emissions and the introduction of green technologies. Andijan is the most favorable in terms of emissions, probably due to the smaller amount of heavy industry. In general, all four regions require improved environmental control, especially in terms of CO₂ and SO₂ emissions.

The current state of environmental management in Uzbekistan. Despite the adopted laws and regulations, environmental policy in the industrial sector faces a number of problems: the lack of clear control mechanisms, insufficient automation of emission accounting and weak law enforcement practice [20].

World experience and its applicability in Uzbekistan. Examples of Germany, South Korea and China show the importance of integrating ISO 14001 environmental standards, developing green technologies and applying the principles of best available technologies (BAT) [21].

Problems and challenges of environmental management in Uzbekistan [22]:

- Insufficient institutional framework
- Limited funding
- Low level of environmental culture
- Worn-out production facilities
- Problems with waste and pollution
- Impact of climate change
- Lack of clear incentives for business

Recommendations for the implementation of sustainable practices:

- Implementation of environmental monitoring systems;
- Stimulating enterprises to certify according to ISO 14001;
- Developing waste management infrastructure;
- Improving the skills of environmental specialists.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Environmental management is becoming an integral part of sustainable industrial development in Uzbekistan. Modern trends (green energy, eco-cities, education reform) show that the country is moving in the right direction. However, serious challenges remain - from lack of funding to a weak environmental culture [23].

To ensure environmental sustainability in industrial clusters, a set of measures is required that cover both the state and corporate levels of management.

Firstly, it is necessary to strengthen inter-industry interaction and coordination on the part of the state. Environmental challenges are systemic in nature, so individual enterprises are not able to effectively address them without support and integration with other industries. The creation of coordinating councils, the development of unified strategies and inter-cluster programs will help to combine the efforts of industry, energy, agriculture and the transport system.

Secondly, an important area is the introduction of environmental standards and innovative technologies at the enterprise level. This involves the transition to environmental management systems, the modernization of production facilities, the introduction of resource-saving and waste-free technologies, as well as the use of renewable energy sources. Thus, each cluster participant will contribute to minimizing the negative impact on the environment.

The third priority is to increase the level of environmental awareness and involvement of businesses and the population. Involvement of small and medium businesses in green innovation projects, organization of training programs and development of corporate social responsibility form a culture of sustainable development and create long-term motivation to reduce environmental risks.

Finally, the active use of green economy mechanisms is of particular importance. This concerns the introduction of financial instruments that stimulate the greening of production: green bonds, tax incentives for environmentally friendly technologies, public-private partnerships in waste recycling. This will not only reduce the burden on the environment, but also increase the competitiveness of industrial clusters in international markets.

Thus, environmental sustainability in industrial clusters is possible only with a combination of government regulation, technological innovations, increased social responsibility of business and the introduction of green economy principles.

In conclusion, the formation of effective environmental management in industrial clusters of Uzbekistan is a prerequisite for the sustainable development of the country. A comprehensive government strategy and the participation of all stakeholders are needed.

List of used literature

1. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Nature Protection". December 9, 1992, No. 754-XII. <https://www.lex.uz/acts/7065>
2. Porter M. The Competitive Advantage of Nations. – New York: Free Press, 1990. – 875 p.
3. Frosch R.A., Gallopoulos N.E. Strategies for Manufacturing // Scientific American. – 1989. – Vol. 261, No. 3. – P. 94–102.
4. Andrews D. Green Management: Principles and Examples. – London: Routledge, 1998. – 212 p.
5. Del Borja A. Environmental Management Systems and Clusters // Journal of Cleaner Production. – 2006. – Vol. 14, No. 9–11. – P. 817–826.
6. Gibbs N., Dixon J. Ecodesign and Cluster Development // Business Strategy and the Environment. – 2002. – Vol. 11, No. 4. – P. 248–257.
7. Chertow M.R. Industrial Symbiosis in Kalundborg // Journal of Industrial Ecology. – 1994. – Vol. 1, No. 1. – P. 67–79.
8. Lee J., Park C. From Industrial Park to Eco-Industrial Park: Patterns of Development in Korea // Journal of Environmental Planning and Management. – 2008. – Vol. 51, No. 1. – P. 23–42.
9. Merrill H. Collaborative Environmental Governance. – Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2010. – 285 p.
10. Hoffman R. Managing Sustainable Innovation in Clusters // Organization & Environment. – 2014. – Vol. 27, No. 4. – P. 353–370.
11. Srivastava S.K. Green Supply-Chain Management: A State-of-the-Art Literature Review // International Journal of Management Reviews. – 2007. – Vol. 9, No. 1. – P. 53–80.
12. Baumann M. Life Cycle Assessment in Industrial Clusters. – Berlin: Springer, 2013. – 190 p.
13. Chen S., Huang H. Digitalization and Eco-Industrial Development // Sustainability. – 2019. – Vol. 11, No. 20. – P. 1–15.

14. Block J., et al. Blockchain for Green Supply Chains // Journal of Cleaner Production. – 2020. – Vol. 264. – P. 121–131.
15. Lombardi P. Eco-Industrial Parks in the European Union. – Brussels: European Commission, 2016. – 156 p.
16. Zhang C. Eco-Industrial Development in China // Journal of Cleaner Production. – 2017. – Vol. 142. – P. 317–329.
17. Andrews R. Environmental Governance in Clusters. – Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2018. – 240 p.
18. Mol A. Measuring Eco-Efficiency in Clusters // Ecological Indicators. – 2020. – Vol. 113. – P. 106–122.
19. Klewitz J., Hansen E. Sustainability-Oriented Innovation in Clusters // Sustainability. – 2014. – Vol. 6, No. 2. – P. 1167–1188.
20. UNEP (2022). Global Environment Outlook. <https://www.unep.org/geo/>
21. Kholikova R.S. Tendencies in the development and Ensuring green security of industrial enterprises in Uzbekistan. Научно-практическая конференция на тему “Зелёная бухгалтерия в Узбекистане: устойчивость и международные стандарты”. International school of finance technology and science. 3 апрель 2025 г.. 553-558 стр.
22. R.S.Kholikova. (2025). Trends in the development and provision of green security of industrial enterprises in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Сборник материалов Международной научно-практической конференции на тему «Перспективные направления достижения целей устойчивого развития и развития зеленой экономики в Узбекистане». Бухарский государственный университет, 14-15 апреля 2025 г., 351-356
23. P.C.Холикова. Опыт зарубежных стран в применении инструментов ИИ в обеспечении экономической безопасности промышленных предприятий. Актуальные проблемы применения искусственного интеллекта в экономике. Республиканская научно-практическая конференция. Сборник статей и тезисов, 14 марта 2025 г. – Т.: Университет общественной безопасности Республики Узбекистан. стр. 220-224.

**TOSHKENT DAVLAT
IQTISODIYOT UNIVERSITETI**

IV GLOBAL VA MILLIY IQTISODIYOT TRENDLARI: “O‘ZBEKISTON – 2030” STRATEGIYASI FORUMI

YASHIL IQTISODIYOT VA TARAQQIYOT

Ilmiy elektron jurnal

(MAXSUS SON)

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o‘g‘li

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo‘yicha ro‘yxatdan o‘tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug‘bek tumani
Kumushkon ko‘chasi, 26-uy.

TASHKENT STATE
UNIVERSITY OF ECONOMICS
AND MATHEMATICS

23-24

OCTOBER
2030

23-24
OCTOBER
2025

1st CONFERENCE:
DIRECTIONS FOR ENSURING
SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC
GROWTH IN THE CONTEXT OF
TRANSITION TO A GREEN ECONOMY

3RD CONFERENCE:
MACHINE LEARNING AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE:
A NEW APPROACH TO ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS

CONFERENCE "GLOBAL
AND NATIONAL ECONOMIC
TRENDS"

UZBEKISTAN
STRATEGY
23-24 OCTOBER

- ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE
AND DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES
- ECONOMETRICS AND
BUSINESS ANALYTICS
- DATA SCIENCE (DATABASES)
- DIGITAL GOVERNMENT
- DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION
- ECONOMIC STATISTICS
- QUANTITATIVE MEASUREMENT
OF THE ECONOMY

2nd CONFERENCE:
BANKING AND
FINANCIAL SYSTEM AND
DIRECTIONS FOR DEVELOPING
THE PRIVATE SECTOR

23-24 2025
OCTOBER

- Makroiqtisodiy barqarorlik
- Yashil iqtisodiyotda
mehnat bozori
- Jahon iqtisodiyoti va xalqaro
iqtisodiy munosabatlar
- Yashil investitsiya va kreditlash
- Yashil texnologiyalar
- Eko turizm
- Yashil innovatsiyalar

СТРАТЕГИЯ
«УЗБЕКИСТАН –2030»

23-24 2025
OCTOBER

- Makroiqtisodiy barqarorlik
- Yashil iqtisodiyotda
mehnat bozori
- Jahon iqtisodiyoti va xalqaro
iqtisodiy munosabatlar
- Yashil investitsiya va kreditlash
- Yashil texnologiyalar
- Eko turizm
- Yashil innovatsiyalar

strategy2025.tsue.uz

YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISH
SHAROITIDA BARQAROR IQTISODIY
O'SISHNI TA'MINLASH YO'NALISHLARI

2030

<https://strategy2025.tsue.uz/>

TASHKENT STATE UNIVERSITY OF ECONOMICS
ФОРУМ UZBEKISTAN
STRATEGY

ISSN: 2992-8982

Elektron pochta: sq1141983@gmail.com

Telefon: +998 93 124 57 11

Sayt: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>

Telegram: https://t.me/taraqqiyot_va_talim_uz

ISBN 978-9910-8110-8-1

9 789910 811081

CONFERENCE "GLOBAL
AND NATIONAL ECONOMIC
TRENDS"

1st CONFERENCE:
DIRECTIONS FOR ENSURING
SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC
GROWTH IN THE CONTEXT OF
TRANSITION TO A GREEN ECONOMY

2030
UZBEKISTAN
STRATEGY

BANK-MOLIYA TIZIMI
VA XUSUSIY SEKTORNI
RIVOJLANTIRISH
YO'NALISHLARI